

QCM-D viscoelastic and adhesion monitoring facilitates label-free and strain-selective bacterial discrimination.

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Abstract

Discriminating bacterial adhesion profiles at strain-specific level is crucial for simulating and predicting infections and persistence, as well as developing more efficient antibacterial therapies. Hereby, we propose that label- and receptor-free bacterial discrimination can be achieved by dynamic viscoelastic and adhesion monitoring over specified timescales using the quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D). Using two closely related *E. coli* strains, ATCC[®] 8739, and JM109(DE3), we show that their viscoelastic and adhesion properties evolve in time through strain-specific profiles that are clearly distinguishable over a period of 3 to 4 hours. In addition, the viscoelasticity of both *E. coli* strains shows a strong strain-specific dependence on the medium ionic strength, allowing to further amplify the differences in the bacterial adhesion signatures. Furthermore, we compared the viscoelastic and adhesion behaviours of the two *E. coli* strains with two additional bacteria, *Citrobacter freundii* and *Serratia marcescens*. For all four bacteria, distinct viscoelastic profiles, and adhesion fingerprints emerge over similar timescales that allow to reliably discriminate the various bacteria. These results, and similar studies on other bacteria might have pharmacological benefits: For instance, by highlighting the role of bacterial-substrate adhesion and viscoelastic properties on disease pathogenesis and persistence, towards developing more effective therapies.

Keywords: QCM-D, cell detection, bacterial adhesion, cell viscoelasticity, antimicrobial therapy, biofilm formation

1 Introduction

The ability to dynamically monitor bacterial adhesion in real time, over long-time scales is crucial for understanding and controlling many aspects of bacterial processes and interactions. For instance, bacterial adhesion is a key factor in biofilm formation, which is strongly linked to many infectious processes [1-4]. Similarly, the persistence propensity of bacteria is associated with their biofilm formation properties [5,6]. In addition, biofilms are a common cause of contamination on medical implants, which often leads to surgical site infections, and thus expensive revision procedures [4]. Therefore, strategies that can discriminate bacterial adhesion profiles at strain-specific level are essential for simulating and predicting the biofilm formation, infection, and persistence properties of various bacteria [7].

Conventionally, techniques for characterizing the adhesion behaviour of bacteria at cell population level utilize either microscopy methods, such as atomic force microscopy (AFM) [8], scanning electron microscopy (SEM) [9], and optical microscopy techniques [10], or approaches based on hydrodynamic shear forces, e.g., wash assays, centrifugation, spinning disk and flow chamber assays [11]. Colony counting and molecular techniques are also common, with the latter often coupled with microscopy [10-14]. At single-cell levels, multiple techniques are available for measuring adhesion forces, including, AFM single cell force spectroscopy (AFM-SCFS), optical tweezers and membrane force probes [14-16]. For a more comprehensive list of available techniques, see references [10, 11, 14]. Commonly used techniques are either invasive because they apply mechanical forces, infrared radiation, conductive coatings, and exposure to vacuums, or require optically transparent substrate materials and dedicated flow-cells for visualization [10]. Specifically, invasive methods and treatments can alter the natural adhesion properties of cells. Finally, time is a crucial factor in bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation because they involve many time-dependent events that hold key information into their mechanisms. Thus, techniques with capabilities for real-time monitoring of bacterial adhesion behaviours under natural or near-natural conditions are necessary [10, 17]. Specifically, studies at the cell population level are relevant for understanding adhesion and biofilm formation because important interaction, such as cell-cell communication and social cooperativity effects are considered [18, 19].

Moreover, as a dynamic and complex process, bacterial adhesion is driven by biological factors that response to a variety of physico-chemical parameters at the substrate/bacterial/medium interfaces, ranging from surface free energy, wettability, surface charge and surface roughness, to ambient factors, such as ionic strength, pH, temperature, and flow rates [20,21]. An ideal

adhesion monitoring platform should therefore permit for easy variation and control of these parameters.

The quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D) provides a fitting platform for this application. QCM-D is a highly sensitive technique that can monitor, in real time, detailed bacteria adhesion events with high time resolution [8, 17]. In addition, QCM-D can effectively detect not only adhesion dynamics, but also mechanical changes of the entire bacterial-medium overlayer on the chip surface of interest, thus providing three dimensional insights into changes occurring within the cell population system [22]. The ability to provide three-dimensional information accurately is further enhanced by the availability of multiple overtones of the fundamental frequency and dissipation signals, with each overtone sensitive to events at different heights above the adhesion-sensor surface [23]. Also, recent forms of the QCM-D device allow for multiplex monitoring, using multiple flow-cells, thus making simultaneous replicate monitoring of adhesion of treated and control samples possible. Furthermore, QCM-D is label-free, minimally invasive, and various physico-chemical parameters, such as temperature, pH, ionic strength, can easily be tuned during measurements.

In this study, we describe a label-free QCM-D-based approach for discriminating bacterial adhesion profiles and viscoelastic fingerprints at strain-specific level. This strategy exploits knowledge of the physical differences that exist between various bacteria, which are capable of conferring strain-specific alterations in their adhesion interactions on surfaces. For instance, bacterial cells differ widely in size and shape: Sizes range from $\approx 0.7 \mu\text{m}$, for instance *Mycoplasmas* and *Pasteurella tularensis* to 1.0 - 10 μm for large cells (e.g., *Bacillus anthracis*). Shapes vary from rounded *Staphylococcus aureus*, or the ellipsoidal *Streptococcus*, to the rod-shaped *Clostridium*, long-filamentous-branched *Actinomyces*, as well as spiral *Treponema pallidum* and comma-shaped *Vibrio cholerae* [24]. The named bacteria are only representative examples. Furthermore, bacteria have surface appendages, such as flagella (3 to 12 μm long, 12 to 30 nm diameter), fimbriae (also called pili) or curli fibers which are all species or strain-specific, in terms of the type of appendage expressed, their size and number expressed and their spatial distribution on the cell-surface. Numbers range from a single flagellum (e.g., *V. cholerae*) to multiple flagella distributed over the entire cell (e.g., *E. coli* and *Proteus vulgaris*). Different types of fimbriae exist which are mainly determined by the adhesin proteins, such as type IV pili in enteropathogenic *E. coli* [25] and type I fimbriae in *Serratia marcescens* [26]. Often, multiple different fimbriae are present on the same bacterium. Also, afimbrial or non-fimbrial adhesins (include protein or polysaccharide structures that are surface exposed on

the bacterial cell and/or secreted) can influence adhesion [27]. All types of appendages play crucial roles in different dynamic aspects of bacterial mechanical properties and adhesion interactions [24, 28 - 33].

Similarly, the role of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) on bacteria has been studied and shown to influence the adhesion mechanisms of EPS-producing bacteria in comparison with non-EPS producing bacteria [31]. In *Citrobacter*, curli fimbriae together with extracellular cellulose are associated with biofilm formation [34]. One also expects marked alterations in the viscoelastic properties of the bacterial-substrate interface when compared between EPS-secreting and non-secreting bacteria, or even within EPS-secreting bacteria, when considering the dynamic evolution of EPS stages in biofilm maturation and dispersal [10].

Overall, the strain-specific nature of these bacterial properties, i.e., size, shape, surface appendages, and EPS secretion might therefore provide opportunities for discriminating bacteria by exploiting the dynamic macroscopic properties that are conferred on the cells (and thus cell-material interfaces) due to these differences. Further parameters that have a strong potential for tuning bacterial-substrate interactions, such as ionic strength might also provide fine-tuned signatures for bacterial discrimination [32, 33].

To date, most dynamic studies on bacterial adhesion, including QCM-based ones focus on short-term initial adhesion, lasting less than a couple of hours, thus limited to the visualization of short-term interaction patterns [32, 33]. Since many dynamic processes involving bacterial-substrate interactions occur in long term (e.g., formation of EPS, biofilm, etc.), important information that shows up over long timescales is often missed in short term studies. Such information could hold the key for discriminating bacteria at strain-specific level.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. QCM-D platform and measurements

Cell-material interactions were monitored using the QCM-D E4 instrument (Q-sense Gothenburg, Sweden). 5 MHz AT-cut quartz crystals with silica (SiO₂) and gold coatings were purchased from Biolin Scientific (Gothenburg, Sweden). The composition and dimensions of the sensor chips are specified in previous work [23,35]. The gold- and SiO₂-coated crystals were cleaned by first exposing them to UV-ozone (UVO-Cleaner[®], Jelight Company Inc., CA, USA) for 15 min and 30 min, respectively. Afterwards, the SiO₂-coated chips were washed with 1% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) solution (Sigma-Aldrich, Diegem, Belgium) and autoclave-sterilized Milli-Q water (resistivity 18.2 MΩcm at 25 °C). The gold-coated chips, after UV-ozone treatment were first washed in a 5:1:1 mixture of Milli-Q water, ammonia and hydrogen peroxide and rinsed in Milli-Q water followed by a final cleaning step in acetone (99% purity). All chips were blow-dried with N₂ gas after the final washing step. Acetone was purchased from VWR International S.A.S, (Fontenay-Sous-Bois, France).

During each measurement, the frequency shift and energy dissipation signals were allowed to equilibrate in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) solution to establish a stable baseline for at least 20 min before exchanging the medium with a suspension of cells. A flow rate of 100 μL/min was used for cell addition to the sensor for a period of 60 min. Cells were then allowed to interact with the sensor surface in stagnant liquid for at least 24 h (T = 37 °C), while the frequency shift, Δf , and dissipation, ΔD , were monitored continuously at a room temperature of 19 ± 0.5 °C. Measurements were repeated at least 3 times based on biological replicates (samples from the same culture). For control, similar measurements were performed in cell-free buffer solutions over the same time scales. Unless otherwise stated, all data analysis was based on the same middle overtone (7th). This is because various overtones have different penetration depths: Lower overtones penetrate deeper into the liquid. For instance, for the 5 MHz shear wave (fundamental mode) propagating in an aqueous medium, the penetration depth is 250 nm [36].

2.2. Bacterial cell preparation and cell cultures

Cell cultures, *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739, *E. coli* JM109(DE3), *Citrobacter freundii* (LMG3246^T), and *Serratia marcescens* (LMG 2792^T), as well as the preparations for measurements were carried out as described in ref. [37]. Optical density (OD600) measurements were employed for determining cell concentrations using the Ocean Optics[™] Red Tide USB650 VIS-NIR Fiber

Optic Spectrometer. Cell suspensions ($\approx 10^6$ cells/mL) were prepared by dispersing bacteria in PBS solutions of different ionic strengths. Buffer solutions of various ionic strengths (0 – 299 mM) were prepared by serial dilutions of $10 \times$ PBS (1491 mM, pH 7.4) in Milli-Q water [23,35]. To prepare $10 \times$ PBS, a mixture of 37.7 g NaCl (> 99 % purity), 4.4 g Na_2HPO_4 (> 99 %), and 1 g KH_2PO_4 (> 99 % purity) was dissolved in 500 mL of Milli-Q water and sterilized by autoclaving. All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Overijse, Belgium).

For the optical visualization of cells, *E. coli* JM109(DE3) bacteria were labelled with the enhanced green fluorescence protein (EGFP). The cells were first transformed by incorporating the fluorescent vector pRSETb-mEmerald (≈ 10 ng plasmid in 50 μL cell suspension). This vector contains sequences that encode the Enhanced Green Fluorescent Protein (EGFP) variant. Mix & Go Competent *E. coli* cells were prepared using a Zymo Research kit (Zymo Research, CA USA) following the instructions of the manufacturer. Transformed cells were spread on a lysogeny broth agar supplemented with ampicillin (LBA-Amp). The cells were grown for 16 - 20 hours at 37 °C and single cell colonies were inoculated in 3 mL LB-Amp for a further growth time of 8 hours at 37 °C on a shaker (200 rpm). Furthermore, the 3 mL cell culture was inoculated in 150 mL LB-Amp followed by a final growth period of 16 – 20 hours at 37 °C. Cells were harvested by centrifuging at 8000 rpm for 5 min at 4 °C and re-suspended in pure $1 \times$ PBS buffer (pH 7.4).

2.3. Microscopy

Optical microscopy was performed on sensor surfaces after QCM-D measurement to confirm the correlation of the dissipation, ΔD , and frequency shift, Δf , with the number of bound cells as a function of ionic strength and surface material (Au and SiO_2). A Leica DM750 M microscope was used, which was equipped with a LED light source (Leica SFL100, excitation at 470 nm \pm 20 nm) and a HD Digital Camera (Leica MC170 HD). To ensure that the sensor surfaces for imaging contained only cells that were attached during measurements, the medium in the QCM-D measuring chamber was exchanged with pure buffer of the same ionic strength (Flow rate = 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 30 mins) and the chips gently blow-dried with N_2 gas.

2. 4. Cell viability measurements

Cell viability measurements were performed using the resazurin reagent (purity > 99%, Acros Organics, ThermoFisher Scientific, Geel, Belgium). Resazurin was prepared as described in refs. [23, 38]. As a measurement principle, metabolically active bacteria reduce the blue resazurin solution to pink resorufin. Thus, the rate of resazurin conversion positively correlates

with cell metabolic activity, and therefore cell viability [39]. To assess bacterial viability as a function of ionic strength, we used *E. coli* JM109(DE3) (10^6 cells/mL). Quantitative analysis of metabolic activity was carried out by measuring the time-dependent fluorescence of resorufin using a microwell plate reader (Tecan infinite 200PRO, Tecan Trading AG, Männedorf, Switzerland). Resorufin fluorescence was monitored at 590 nm wavelength with a sampling rate of one measurement every 2.5 min for a period of 4 hours. All measurements were performed at 37 °C.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Dynamic viscoelastic properties and adhesion of *E. coli* ATCC® 8739

Figure 1 shows the time dependent dissipation, ΔD , and frequency shift, Δf , resulting from the interaction of *E. coli* ATCC® 8739 (1×10^6 cells/mL) on a gold-coated QCM-D surface for a period of 40 h. The medium was composed of 149 mM ionic strength (i.e., 1×PBS) and as shown in **Figure 1a**, the dissipation increases to 8.6×10^{-6} before slightly decreasing to 8.1×10^{-6} in the long term. All overtones follow the same time-dependent trend, and this behaviour of the dissipation is consistent with long-term dissipative behaviour of *E. coli* JM109(DE3) reported in ref. [20]. An increase in the dissipation signal depicts a higher viscoelasticity of the bacterial over-layer on the sensor while the slight decrease in the long term can be attributed to increased stiffness due to reorganization of the bacterial cytoskeleton and/or restructuring of the surface appendages towards establishing a stronger adhesive contact [33].

The corresponding frequency shift, Δf , displayed in **Figure 1b** decreases to 16.7 Hz as cells are added to the surface. The decrease in the frequency shift is also observed for other overtones. A small temporal and partial recovery is observed as the system transitions from flow to non-flow. This recovery is seen for all overtones, and occurs incrementally later for the higher overtones compared to the lower ones. For the reference measurement on a sample consisting of a 149 mM ionic strength medium without cells, the dissipation and frequency signals exhibit little (noise-level) or no changes. **Figure 1c** shows frequency and dissipation values from different overtones compared between the reference sample (149 mM PBS without bacteria) and the sample with bacteria. The 1st overtone displays considerable time-dependent fluctuations and is thus not included for simplicity. Data points are the mean of at least three measurements and determined from the raw signals at $t = 20$ h, while the error bars are the standard deviations.

Figure 1. Viscoelastic properties and adhesion of *E. coli* ATCC® 8739. **a, b):** Time dependent dissipation, ΔD , and frequency, Δf , due to *E. coli* (1×10^6) adhesion on a gold-coated QCM-D surface. Reference measurement in pure PBS buffer of the same ionic strength (149 mM) included. **c):** Frequency and dissipation compared by overtone number for a reference sample (149 mM PBS only) and bacterial sample at $t = 20$ h, showing differences for all overtones. **d, e):** Dissipation and frequency plots as a function of ionic strength, showing more distinctive incremental pattern for the dissipation. **f):** Comparison of frequency and dissipation at $t = 20$ h, for bacteria in 149 mM and 299 mM ionic strengths as a function of overtone number. The data points in c) and f) are the mean of at least three measurements calculated from the time point, $t = 20$ h, while the errors are the standard deviations.

For all overtones, the frequency and dissipation values are markedly higher when compared with the values from the reference measurement, meaning that they reflect bacterial interactions. One observes a drift in the magnitude of the frequency shifts towards high values

for lower overtones, which is more pronounced for the lowest overtones. This drift is also seen in the reference measurement, although to a lesser extent. The lower overtones also tend to show a larger variability as seen in the size of the error bars. This might be due to the stronger interaction of these overtones with the liquid medium, since they penetrate deeper, compared to higher overtones.

To highlight the effect of ionic strength, we focus the analysis on the first 20 h of measurements because over this time frame, the differences in the profiles as a function of ionic strength are stable. As shown in **Figure 1d**, by varying the ionic strength from 0 mM to 299 mM, we show that the long-term dissipation and frequency signals (**Figure 1e**) are strongly modulated by the medium ionic strength. That is, higher ionic strengths result in larger adhesion responses. In particular, the dissipation shows a more distinctive incremental response to changing ionic strength in comparison with the frequency shift. This suggests that dissipation monitoring might be a more reliable parameter for monitoring the bacterial-substrate interactions. This is consistent with the reference measurement shown in **Figure 1a** for which the dissipation displays less drift as opposed to a larger Δf change (**Figure 1b**). The small recovery of the frequency signal during the initial stationary adhesion phase (non-flow) is also observed for all ionic strengths. Specifically, as the ionic strength increases, the recovery regime becomes more pronounced, in terms of both magnitude and time. The differences in the frequency and dissipations as a function of ionic strength are also displayed by other overtones. As an example, **Figure 1f**, shows consistently higher Δf and ΔD values for 299 mM in comparison with 149 mM for all overtones.

Specifically, for 299 mM, following the small recovery after cell addition, one observes a steady increase in the magnitudes of Δf and ΔD , a behaviour that becomes less pronounced for lower ionic strengths. This can be attributed to a gradual increase in the cell-substrate contact area. The appendages of bacteria confer complex dynamic adhesion processes, in which cells first establish contact through these extended surface structures, before subsequently establishing cell-body-substrate contact [20, 33]. For cells in 0 mM ionic strength, the dissipation remains approximately at the zero level while the frequency shift in the long term (e.g., $t > 15$ h), changes only slightly. This indicates that these cells display very minimal interaction (and thus adhesion) in this ion-free medium.

The maximum dissipation and frequency shifts, representing the maximum adhesion levels are displayed in **Figure 2** for the various ionic strengths: 0, 19, 37, 75, 149, 224, and 299 mM. Each data point is an average of at least three measurements and the errors are the standard deviations.

Figure 2. Dissipation and adhesion properties of *E. coli* ATCC® 8739 as a function of ionic strength. Dissipation, (a) and frequency (b) for the 7th overtone, showing an incremental rise in both parameters with ionic strength. Data points correspond to the maximum Δf and ΔD values.

The values of the frequency and dissipation shifts for cells in the ion-free medium (0 mM) are practically within the noise-level, confirming that the bacterial interaction with the gold surface is significantly counteracted. This effect can (at least partly) be attributed to repulsive interactions at the bacteria-chip interface. In confirmation, measurements of the electrophoretic mobility of various *E. coli* strains by Gutman *et al.*, showed ionic strength dependence: The magnitude of electrophoretic mobilities decreased with increasing ionic strength for all bacterial strains, indicating that the bacterial surface charge is tuned [22]. This suggests that an ion-free medium can play an important role in bacterial antifouling applications. In the presence of ions, for instance, for the lowest ionic strength (19 mM), one observes a clear shift in the dissipation and frequency above noise level, which increases with ionic strength. The frequency data exhibits large variability in comparison with the dissipation trend. This further highlights dissipation monitoring as a more reliable parameter for describing and predicting bacterial-substrate interactions.

3.2 Surface-dependent adhesion of *E. coli* ATCC® 8739

Here, we show that ionic strength also influences long-term bacterial adhesion on silica. A comparison of *E. coli* ATCC® 8739 adhesion on SiO₂ and Au is provided in **Figure 3** for two ionic strengths, 149 mM, and 299 mM. For SiO₂, the maximum changes in the dissipation, ΔD (**Figure 3a**), and frequency, Δf (**Figure 3b**) during adhesion are higher for the 299 mM ionic strength, confirming that ionic strength also enhances *E. coli* adhesion on SiO₂. Compared

between Au and SiO₂, for each ionic strength, the maximum shifts in ΔD and Δf are higher for Au. In terms of the mechanisms, ionic strength controls the thickness of the electrical double layer, which results in a decrease in the long-range electrostatic repulsion and promotes cell-substrate contact [40-43]. Literature studies on short-term bacteria adhesion confirm that an ionic strength increase in the range of 0 - 300 mM shrinks the electrical double layer and enhance bacterial adhesion [21, 32, 36, 43, 44]. This is consistent with the increasing adhesion of *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 as the ionic strength increases from 0 to 299 mM (**Figure 1c** and **1d**; **Figure 2**). Here, we note that the 0 mM (pure water) medium can also form double layers on cells and the sensor surfaces, due to the dissociation of water into negative hydroxide (OH⁻) and positive hydronium (H₃O⁺) ions [45, 46]. Thus, a pure water medium can contribute to long-range coulombic, as well as short-range hydration repulsive forces between cells and surfaces [35].

The low adhesion interactions on SiO₂ can be attributed to its highly negative surface charge [20]. A highly negative surface charge is associated with a strong long-range repulsion due a larger electrical double layer as well as the acid-base repulsion originating from the electron-donor component that dominates the silica surface. This component is much smaller for Au, on which van der Waals interactions dominate. A comprehensive characterization of the interfacial surface properties of SiO₂ and Au in the light of cell-material interactions is provided in refs. [32,35].

Figure 3. Surface and Ionic strength-dependent *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 adhesion. Comparison of dissipation, ΔD (a), and frequency, Δf (b), between Au and SiO₂ during *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 adhesion. The cell concentration was uniformly 1×10^6 cells/mL.

3.3 Ionic strength tunes adhesion and viscoelasticity of *E. coli* JM109(DE3)

We also studied the long-term adhesion of a second strain of *E. coli*, being *E. coli* JM109(DE3). **Figure 4** compares the dissipation (a) and frequency shift (b) in response to the adhesion of

this bacteria on gold for three ionic strengths, 0, 149 and 299 mM. The dissipation for cells in MilliQ water (0 mM) remains approximately the same before and after the 1-hour cell injection (i.e., at $\approx 0 \times 10^{-6}$). This behaviour is comparable to the dissipative pattern for the *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 cells in 0 mM (**Figure 1c and 1d**). The frequency, however, displays a shift of ≈ 15 Hz after cell addition, which is much higher, in comparison with *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739. Similar to the behaviour of *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739, ΔD shows a distinctive increase as the ionic strength increases from 149 to 299 mM. For Δf , one observes a fast adhesion kinetics that results in an initial, and clearly higher value for 149 mM compared to 299 mM, with the latter catching up in the long term.

Figure 4. Ionic strength tunes adhesion and viscoelasticity of *E. coli* JM109(DE3). Dissipation, ΔD (a), and frequency, Δf (b), due to *E. coli* JM109(DE3) adhesion on Au for a 1×10^6 cell concentration. (c) Optical images of rinsed Au and SiO₂ surfaces after measurements in 0 mM and 149 mM ionic strengths showing a higher cell coverage for the higher ionic strengths as well as more bound cells on Au in comparison with SiO₂.

The correlation of *E. coli* adhesion with ionic strength is also depicted by the optical images in **Figure 4c**. As shown by fluorescence imaging, there are considerably more bound bacteria on the Au surface for 149 mM compared to 0 mM (upper panels). The lower panel shows a similar trend for images obtained on SiO₂ surfaces. When compared between silica and gold surfaces, the latter contains more bound bacteria than the former.

The lack of a direct linear correlation between the frequency and the dissipation signals, which is observed for both *E. coli* strains is interesting (**Figures 1d,e and Figures 4a,b**). This could be partly explained by the biological factors that affect the dissipation and frequency magnitudes. For instance, the distance at which the bacterial body is held from the QCM sensor surface by surface appendages [36], as well as the nature and extent of bacterial secretions (e.g., EPS) to the substrate [31]. It has been shown that colanic acid, the EPS produced by *E. coli* K12, is required not for initial attachment to an abiotic surface, but rather for establishing the complex three-dimensional structure of an *E. coli* biofilm [47]. By studying *Streptococcus salivarius* mutants, expressing varied surface appendages Olsson *et al.* showed that the frequency shift produced by bacteria with surface appendages was not proportional to the number of adhered bacteria. The authors attributed this non-linear relationship to the dependence of the frequency shift on the overtone number, as lower ones tend to sense freely mobile surface appendages, while the higher overtones sense the cell body. On the other hand, they showed that, while only bald bacteria showed a linear correlation between the overall frequency shifts and the number of attached bacteria, all bacterial strains (with or without appendages) displayed a linear correlation between the dissipation and the number of attached bacteria on the sensor surface [36]. This is consistent with our observations in which the frequency trends display deviations from the dissipation trends. From a physico-chemical point of view, there is also the possibility that ionic strength affects the frequency and dissipation parameters through different mechanisms, thus resulting in a discrepancy between their trends. For instance, how each QCM-D parameter responds to changes in the electrophoretic properties of the cells, such as bacterial double layer thickness, its effect on the apparent cell stiffness as well as on the gravitational force on the cells. This hypothesis is covered in detail in reference [23]. In addition, changes in ionic strength are also known to correlate with alterations in turgor pressure and the elasticity of cells as well as their appendages [1, 48].

3.4 Long-term dissipation monitoring distinguishes adhesion properties of *E. coli* strains

To show that long-term adhesion is useful for label- and receptor-free bacterial discrimination of adhesion properties, we compared the adhesion patterns of the two closely related bacterial strains discussed in Sections 3.1 – 3.3, i.e., ATCC[®] 8739 and JM109(DE3). **Figure 5a** compares the dissipation, ΔD , at 149- and 299-mM ionic strengths. As shown for each ionic strength, the ΔD is much higher for *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739. Specifically, for both ionic strengths, the differences in the ΔD signals are less discernible during the adsorption phase, but become clearly distinguishable in the long term. Additionally, as shown in **Figure 5b**, which is an expansion of **Figure 5a**, the higher ionic strength provides larger differences, indicating that ionic tuning can be useful for more optimal discrimination.

To demonstrate the reliability/reproducibility of these results, we calculated the average ΔD signal from at least three independent measurements for the 149 mM ionic strength at various time points: 20 min, 1.5 h, 4 h, 8 h, 20 h, and 40 h (**Figure 5c**). The error bars are the standard deviations. One observes a similar trend as in the raw data (**Figure 5a**): i) In terms of the time-dependent profile for each bacterium, and ii) in relation to the difference in the ΔD values compared between the two strains.

Figure 5. Long-term dissipation and adhesion fingerprints distinguish *E. coli* strains. **a)** Comparison of dissipation signals, ΔD , between two *E. coli* strains, *E. coli* ATCC® 8739 and *E. coli* JM109(DE3) for two ionic strengths, 149 and 299 mM (see arrow heads). **b)** Expansion of **a)** showing a larger difference in the ΔD signals of the two bacterial strains over long-time scales of 8 hours for both ionic strengths compared to the short-term response (e.g., 60 min as indicated by the box). **c)** Plots of ΔD values at various time points for at least 3 measurements at 149 mM, compared between the two strains and displaying the emergence of differences over time. Adhesion fingerprints distinguish *E. coli* strains, ATCC® 8739 and JM109(DE3). **d,e)** Dissipation vs. frequency (df) plots compared between two *E. coli* strains, ATCC® 8739 and JM109(DE3) for 149 mM (**d**) and 299 mM (**e**) on Au. For both ionic strengths, the slope of the df plot is higher for ATCC® 8739 than JM109(DE3). The dotted lines (tangential) are guides to the eye in relation to the general slope of the df plot during the cell adsorption phase.

Apart from being useful for bacterial differentiation of adhesion properties, the identification of such large time-dependent differences might have pharmacological benefits: For instance, since bacterial adhesion drives biofilm formation, dynamic adhesion and viscoelastic trends might reveal strain-specific differences in biofilm formation mechanisms. In turn, this can provide further insights into bacterial infection mechanisms and strain-specific persistence propensity [2-5,49].

3.5 Adhesion fingerprints distinguish *E. coli* strains, ATCC® 8739 and JM109(DE3)

We now analyse the dissipation and frequency in combination, by plotting the dissipation as a function of the frequency shift (*df* plots). Such plots are often called the adhesion fingerprints because their slopes reflect the cytoskeletal changes that follow cell adhesion interactions independent of the cell concentration and spatial distribution on the sensor chip [20,50,51]. Due to the dissipative (viscoelastic) properties of cells, the frequency shift during adhesion only reflects a fraction of the cell mass [50,51]. Consequently, *df* plots are potentially attractive as signatures for discriminating various bacterial cells and their cell-specific adhesion mechanisms [20].

Figures 5d,e show the *df* plots for *E. coli* strains, ATCC® 8739 and JM109(DE3) for 149 mM and 299 mM ionic strengths. The slope of the *df* plots indicates the stiffness of the cells, and consequently, the extent of cytoskeletal organization. The smaller the slope, the stiffer/more organized the cytoskeleton [20,23,51]. For the two ionic strengths, the slope of the *df* plots for the ATCC® 8739 strain is higher in comparison with the JM109(DE3) strain. In addition, the evolution of the slopes as a function of time also varies by bacterial type. For illustration, the dotted lines in **Figures 5 d,e** highlight the slopes of the *df* plots in the cell adsorption phase. The lines are tangential to the general trend of the *df* plot in the adsorption regime. In each case, the slopes are markedly lower for JM109(DE3), depicting a relatively higher stiffness of the cell overlayer. The large increase in the *df* slopes from 149 mM to 299 mM for both cells indicates that indeed, the ionic strength increases the viscoelasticity of cells.

It is known that different *E. coli* strains can have very diverse adhesion characteristics which are cell-specific, host-specific, or tissue/substrate-specific. This indicates that *E. coli* displays a broad variety of different colonization strategies, including expression of different adhesins [52]. It is therefore not surprising that the two *E. coli* strains used in this study also display different adhesion fingerprints, as revealed by the QCM-D data.

3.6 Viscoelastic and adhesion monitoring enable label-free bacterial differentiation.

In addition to studying the two *E. coli* strains, we performed measurements on two additional bacterial species, *Citrobacter freundii* (LMG3246^T) and *Serratia marcescens* (LMG 2792^T), which like *E. coli* also belong to the order of Enterobacterales. For simplicity, we focused on the 149 mM ionic strength measurements for comparing the four bacterial strains (same bacterial concentrations).

Figure 6. Viscoelastic and adhesion monitoring provide label free bacterial differentiation. **a)** Time dependent dissipation, ΔD , plots for representative measurements on four bacteria. **b)** Comparison of the average ΔD values at $t = 40$ h (see dotted vertical line in a) for various bacteria. **c)** Frequency, Δf , plots for representative measurements for four bacteria on Au showing bacteria-specific profiles. The average Δf values at $t = 40$ h are displayed in **d)**. Generally, the Δf trend is opposite to the ΔD trend. Error bars in **b)** and **d)** are standard deviations.

Figure 6a displays the time-dependent ΔD data for representative measurements. The results show distinctly different dissipation signals when compared between the four strains. These differences are less clear during the cell adsorption phase. To demonstrate reproducibility, we determined the average dissipation after 40 hours (see dotted line) for at least three measurements for each bacteria type (**Figure 6b**). The error bars in **Figure 6b** are the standard

deviations. One observes the same trend in the average ΔD values compared between the various bacteria (**Figure 6b**) as in the raw dissipation values in **Figure 6a**. Also, the four bacteria strains display distinctly different frequency shifts (**Figures 6c,d**), with each bacterial signal displaying unique time-dependent evolution. For instance, in terms of either the initial Δf shift, which is highest for JM109(DE3) and lowest for *C. freundii* (LMG3246TM), or in terms of the signal recovery. On average, bacteria with high dissipation values display low frequency shifts and the reverse holds.

Figure 7. Strain-specific bacteria adhesion profiles evolve over long time scales. **a – f**) Dissipation, ΔD , values at various time points, 20 min, 1.5 h, 4 h, 8 h, 20 h and 40 h after cell injection, displaying the evolution of clear and consistent differential patterns between the four bacteria over long time scales $> 4h$. Each data point was calculated from at least three measurements (biological replicates) and the errors are the standard deviations. **g**) Summary of the data in **a – f**. **h**) Strain-specific viscoelastic changes during bacterial adhesion: The Δf slope, and its time-evolution is characteristic of the bacterial type.

We also compared the dissipation values of the different bacteria over various time points to illustrate the benefit of long-term monitoring towards bacterial discrimination and for revealing cell-type adhesion mechanisms. Time points were considered from the start of cell injection and included, 20 min, 1.5 h, 4 h, 8 h, 20 h and 40 h. As shown, no clear patterns are seen within the first 120 min during and after cell injection (**Figures 7a,b**). Consistent patterns/differences start emerging at ≈ 4 hours after injection (**Figure 7c**) and these patterns remain over long time scales, as depicted in **Figures 7d – 7f**. This confirms that long term bacteria monitoring is required for revealing cell-type specific adhesion characterization. The results in **Figures 7a – f** are summarized in **Figure 7g**.

In addition to measuring changes in mass loading and viscoelasticity using the QCM-D platform [20,53,54], other strategies could be employed to assess the cell-specific changes that follow the various cell adhesion events. For instance, techniques that employ changes in the electrical impedance properties at the chip-liquid-cell interfaces [55-58]. This may help to further elucidate the differences in adhesion mechanisms between species and strains, because adhesion is a multifactorial process involving cell surface characteristics such as hydrophobicity, different types and number of appendages, such as fimbriae, flagella and/or curli, as well as EPS, as described for members of the Enterobacteriaceae [59].

3.7 Strain-specific viscoelastic changes during bacterial adhesion

Finally, we compared the df plots for equal concentrations of all four bacterial strains in 149 mM ionic strength (**Figure 7h**). Each bacterial strain displays unique df profiles, which differ more and more from each other with time. This confirms that major differences in the bacteria-substrate interaction mechanisms emerge over long-term measurements. This might in turn explain the differences in the adhesion and biofilm formation mechanisms of different bacteria. This may help to compare strains in relation to their infection mechanisms as well as their persistence mechanisms, thus, providing therapeutic benefits.

3.8. Cell viability assessment

Towards assessing the role of ionic strength on the viability of the bacterial cells, we measured the metabolic activity as a function of time using the resazurin assay as described in the Materials and Methods: Metabolic activity is measured in terms of the rate of conversion of resazurin to resorufin. The results are displayed in **Figure 8** for three repeated measurements (R1, R2 and R3) on *E. coli* JM109(DE3). As shown (**Figures 8a – e**), the evolution of the resorufin fluorescence signal is similar when compared between the different ionic strengths.

This suggests that the ionic strengths did not negatively impact the metabolic activity of the cells. Therefore, the differences in bacterial adhesion and viscoelasticity as a function of ionic strengths are due to the cell-substrate interaction of similarly viable cells. We note the faster increase in fluorescence when compared between the 0 mM (ion free) medium and the other concentrations. While this difference is relatively small, the result is consistent with a similar study on yeast, which showed much larger differences in yeast resazurin reduction in 0 mM buffer compared to ion-rich buffers [23].

Figure 8. Time dependent metabolic activity of *E. coli* measured by resorufin fluorescence. **a – e**): Resorufin fluorescence for different ionic strengths (0 – 299 mM) showing similar exponential evolution as a function of magnitude and time, thus indicating that cells display similar metabolic activity across the different ionic strengths. The curves for cells in 0 mM evolve to a maximum faster, showing that the cells in this medium are metabolically more active. **f**): Comparison of fluorescence curves between cells in different ionic strengths and reference samples consisting of buffers of different ionic strengths in resazurin without cells. **g**) Images of cuvettes containing cell suspensions of various ionic strengths at 37 °C. Images were acquired from the moment of resazurin addition ($t = 0$ h) and at 20 h after.

Figure 8f compares the fluorescence for cells in various ionic strengths and control samples, consisting of solutions of different ionic strengths (0, 149, and 299 mM) without cells. The

control samples show similar fluorescence signals over the entire 4 h measurement time, proving that the salt concentration did not affect the results of the metabolic activity experiments. To confirm the quantitative correlation of resorufin fluorescence with ionic strength, we acquired images of cuvettes containing the bacterial suspensions at the moment of incubation in resazurin ($t = 0$ h) and 20 h after. The temperature was uniformly $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (The same as the adhesion monitoring temperature), and as displayed in **Figure 8g**, there is a clear change in the colour from blue to pink for all ionic strengths, with a higher intensity for the 0 mM- and 75 mM ionic strength samples, which is consistent with the assay measurements shown in **Figures 8a-e**.

4 Conclusion

In this study, we explored the long-term dissipation and cell-surface interactions of various bacterial strains towards identifying bacterial-specific profiles that allow investigation of adhesion properties. As a starting point, we analysed the interaction of *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 as a model bacterium on Au and SiO₂. Our results show that *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 displays little or no dissipative and adhesive properties in ion-free medium on Au. From ion-free to ion-rich medium, one observes a dramatic jump in the dissipation and adhesion interactions, which both increase with increasing ionic strength. The effect of ionic strength was also confirmed on SiO₂, on which much less adhesion was measured in comparison with Au. Interesting, we showed that the viscoelasticity signals (dissipation), and mass-loading signals (frequency shift) do not follow the same patterns as a function of ionic strength: The dissipation increases incrementally with ionic strength (0 – 299 mM), while for the frequency, this relationship is not linear. We attribute this discrepancy to a combination of physico-chemical factors (e.g., absorbed charged effects) and biological factors, such as, surface appendages and bacterial secretions. As a result, we propose dissipation monitoring as a more reliable indicator for probing bacterial cell-material interactions.

We also compared the adhesion of the two closely related bacterial strains, *E. coli* ATCC[®] 8739 and *E. coli* JM109(DE3). We show that for every ionic strength, the frequency response for JM109(DE3) is higher, but its associated dissipation is always smaller in comparison with ATCC[®] 8739. We also demonstrate that major differences in the bacterial-substrate interactions only emerge in the long term of about 4 hours and over, meaning that short term studies fall short of capturing important dynamic bacteria-specific behaviours and interaction mechanisms. Taking all these differences into consideration in the df plots, we show that fine-tuned

discrimination between the two *E. coli* strains can be facilitated by means of fingerprint (*df*) plots.

Finally, we compared the behaviour of the two *E. coli* strains with two additional bacteria, *C. freundii* (LMG3246^T) and *S. marcescens* (LMG 2792^T). These measurements also confirm that long-term viscoelastic and adhesion monitoring provides reliable receptor- and label-free bacteria discrimination. The observation that differences in bacteria-substrate interaction patterns are better revealed from long-term monitoring has the potential to provide strain-specific information on many important bacteria-material interaction mechanisms, such as biofilm formation and infection processes, as well as persistence, all of which occur over long-time scales of hours.

We note that the results described in this study involve measurements on single bacterial strains. Since biofilms are often complex, similar studies on mixtures of different bacteria might provide more insights into relevant aspects of biofilm formation dynamics.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

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